

Functionalization of SWCNTs: Impact on Tensile Properties and Morphology of CNT-Paper

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Abstract

Carbon nanotube papers prepared from chemically functionalized SWCNTs are investigated for their mechanical tensile properties. The Young's moduli are found to be unaffected by the functionalization with diazonium salts of aniline or aromatic mono- and bis-amides. Tensile strengths of CNT papers, however, are found to increase with increasing degree of functionalization, and more pronouncedly with increasing number of amide groups capable of hydrogen bonding. The importance of hydrogen bonding becomes evident after its inhibition through N-methylation of the amide groups, resulting in a distinct reduction of strength values. SEM analysis indicates that a high degree of functionalization or a high number of amide groups results in the formation of domains with aligned CNTs.

1 Introduction

The exceptional properties reported for individual carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have raised hopes for their application as high-performance structural and functional materials. However, macroscopic materials presented to date have exploited no more than a small fraction of the individual CNT's theoretical potential. Even fibers of aligned CNTs show disappointing tensile strengths, unless the gauge length in the measurement is chosen to be small [1]. Because of the weak intertubular interactions, small structural defects such as inclusions, voids or entanglements are sufficient to significantly reduce the performance of CNT-materials. In order to create stronger CNT-materials, it is necessary to increase the intertubular interactions and thus enhance load transfer.

In this study, short and stiff sidegroups were chemically grafted to the surface of single-walled

carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) and the resulting material processed into CNT paper, a thin mat consisting of randomly in-plane oriented CNTs. CNT paper is easily prepared by vacuum filtration of CNT suspensions. The groups selected for surface functionalization were aniline (**1**), p-amino-N-phenylbenzamide (**2**) and p-[(p-aminobenzoyl)-amino]-N-phenylbenzamide (**3**). **2** and **3** are aromatic amides with one and two amide links, respectively. The presence of such groups promises enhanced intertubular interactions due to the formation of hydrogen bonds and π - π interactions. Also, steric effects are expected to result in higher resistance against lateral displacement of adjacent CNTs and CNT bundles. Overall, increased intertubular interactions are expected to result in higher mechanical strength of such CNT-paper as compared to non-functionalized reference CNT-paper.

2 Experimental

2.1 Functionalization of SWCNTs

High purity single-walled carbon nanotubes (>90% SWCNTs; HeJi Inc., Hong Kong) and commercially obtained reagents were used as received. Aromatic amines **2** and **3** were synthesized stepwise starting from aniline **1** (Fig. 1). A similar reaction sequence has been published by others [2]. Melting ranges and NMR spectra suggested high purity of the crude products, which were employed for CNT functionalization without further purification.

100 mg of SWCNTs together with 1 mol eq. (per mol CNT carbon atoms) aromatic amine **1-3** and 20 ml NMP were added in a 100 ml flask and homogenized in an ultrasonic bath with gradual heating to 60°C. Isopentyl nitrite (1.17 g, 1.2 mol eq.) was added dropwise to the dispersion and

a: 4-nitrobenzoyl chloride, *N,N*-dimethylaniline, acetone, 0°C → r.t.; **b:** Pd (10% on activated charcoal), ammonium formate, DMF, 0°C → r.t.

Fig. 1. Synthesis of amines **2** and **3**

Fig. 2. Sidewall functional groups grafted to CNTs

sonication continued for another 120 min at 60°C. After cooling to room temperature, the CNTs were filtered off with a microporous membrane and washed with NMP until the filtrate was colourless. The NMP-wet CNTs were removed from the filter and used for CNT paper preparation without further treatment. The corresponding functionalized CNTs are designated **1-**, **2-** and **3-CNT** in the following (Fig. 2).

2.2 N-methylation of amide links

Batches of **2-** and **3-CNT** were N-methylated with sodium hydride and iodomethane in dry DMF (Fig. 3). 55% sodium hydride in oil (0.15 g, 6.3 mmol) and dry DMF (7 ml) were stirred at room

Fig. 3. N-methylation of functionalized CNTs

temperature for 10 min. The NMP-moist **2-** or **3-CNT**-paste prepared from 100 mg SWCNTs (as described above) was added all at once. After stirring for 30 min, iodomethane (0.31 ml, 5 mmol) was added to the suspension. After 1.5 h remaining iodomethane was removed from the reaction mixture by evacuation for 10 min. Excess sodium hydride was decomposed by addition of ethanol. CNTs were filtered off and washed with NMP before CNT paper preparation. N-methylated CNTs are designated **m2-** and **m3-CNT** for N-methylated **2-** and **3-** functionalized SWCNTs, respectively.

2.3 Preparation of CNT papers

Functionalized CNTs prepared from 100 mg SWCNTs (as described above) were sonicated in NMP (250 ml) for 45 min with a Hielscher UP 200S ultrasonic processor and cooled with ice during the process. Subsequently, the dispersion was centrifuged for 30 min at 4000 RCF in order to remove remaining agglomerates. 80 vol% of the supernatant dispersion was carefully removed by pipette and filtered through a microporous membrane with the aid of vacuum. The filtration was stopped before the filter ran dry and the remaining layer of approx. 5 mm suspension was discarded and the CNT paper washed with 2-propanol. While still wet, the CNT paper was peeled off the filter and placed between silicone rubber sheets and dried overnight in vacuum at 80°C.

2.4 Analysis of CNT papers

The degree of chemical functionalization of the SWCNTs was assessed by thermo-gravimetric

analysis (Perkin Elmer Pyris 1 TGA) of small CNT paper samples under nitrogen atmosphere. Young's modulus and tensile strength were determined by quasistatic tensile testing (Zwick Roell Z005) of CNT paper strips with a width of 3-4 mm using a clamping distance of 10 mm. CNT paper thickness was determined using a digital micrometer caliper with flat jaws. CNT paper surface morphology was examined using a Zeiss LEO 1530 Gemini scanning electron microscope.

3 Results and discussion

Functionalization of SWCNTs was accomplished using in-situ generated diazonium salts of the respective amines (Fig. 2). The method essentially follows the solvent-free approach of Dyke and Tour [3], but here NMP was added to suspend the comparatively large amounts of solid reactants. In order to assess the impact of hydrogen bonding on mechanical properties, batches of **2-** and **3-CNT** were subjected to N-methylation with iodomethane and sodium hydride as a base, prior to CNT paper preparation. N-methylation of amides effectively disrupts hydrogen bonding by inhibiting the amide's H-donor capability.

CNT papers were prepared by filtration of CNT dispersions in NMP through microporous membranes. Prior to filtration, the dispersions were centrifuged in order to remove larger agglomerates, a procedure previously shown to result in CNT papers with enhanced mechanical properties [4]. Dispersibility in NMP, as determined from the mass

of the CNT papers produced, was found to be unaffected by the chemical functionalization, with the exception of SWCNTs bearing N-methylated sidegroups (Tab. 1) and displaying significantly better dispersibility. The highest concentration was found for **m3-CNT** (411 mg/l), exceeding even the value found for **m2-CNT** (382 mg/l) despite the latter's higher degree of functionalization. While functionalization in general appears not to significantly reduce the mismatch between solubility parameters of CNTs and solvent, N-methylation of the aromatic amides does have an appreciable effect. N-alkylation is known to produce materials with increased solubility in most organic solvents compared to non-alkylated amide linkages [5, 6].

The degree of functionalization was determined on CNT paper samples via the TGA mass loss at 800°C in nitrogen atmosphere as compared to a non-functionalized reference. At this temperature, mass loss had ceased in all samples. The values given in Tab. 1 indicate that heavier molecules used in the functionalization resulted in lower degrees of functionalization as depicted in Fig. 4. This trend is largely consistent with reported data for similar functionalization schemes [3, 7]. Within the limits of TGA, N-methylation of **2-** and **3-CNT** was found to not alter the CNT's degree of functionalization (Tab. 1)

Since the densities of all functionalized CNT papers samples increased by approx. 20% relative to the non-functionalized reference (Tab. 1), mechanical properties were normalized. The respective density-

Tab. 1. Selected properties of functionalized SWCNTs. All values reported were determined on CNT papers prepared from NMP dispersions. Standard deviations are given where applicable.

SWCNT-functionalization	none	1	2	3	m2	m3
NMP-dispersion conc. [mg/l]	263±40	278±32	273±51	279±39	382±11	411±29
TGA residue @ 800°C [%]	81.0	64.5	62.3	65.7	59.1	61.0
deg. of funct. [mol/mol C]	n/a	0.029	0.014	0.007	0.016	0.009
bulk density [g/cm ³]	0.84±0.11	0.98±0.09	1.00±0.16	1.02±0.07	0.97±0.14	1.02±0.06
thickness* [µm]	47±4	43±3	41±4	41±6	58±4	61±4
Young's modulus [N/tex]	1.33±0.36	1.60±0.37	1.46±0.14	1.42±0.32	1.82±0.21	1.08±0.30
strength [mN/tex]	4.79±1.28	8.09±1.96	6.30±1.03	9.60±1.16	4.83±0.58	2.17±0.78

* of circular CNT paper (diameter 41 mm) prepared from 100 mg SWCNT starting material

Fig. 4. Resulting degree of functionalization after reaction of amines **1**, **2** and **3** with SWCNTs

normalized dimensions of Young's modulus and tensile strength are $\text{N}\cdot\text{tex}^{-1}$ and $\text{mN}\cdot\text{tex}^{-1}$. This accounts for the porous morphology of CNT papers and the resulting variation in effective cross-sectional area.

For measured Young's moduli, no significant variation is apparent (see Table 1), irrespective of applied type and degree of functionalization. From a mechanical point of view, CNT papers are similar to an open-celled elastic-brittle cellular solid in which linear elasticity is dictated by cell wall bending [8]. In CNT papers, these cell walls consist of CNT bundles which's bending stiffness is considered largely independent of chemical functionalization.

CNT papers behave brittle and their ultimate tensile strength values scatter considerably. Nevertheless, an impact of functionalization on material strength is evident. As visible in Fig. 5, both **1-CNT** and **2-CNT** papers were stronger than the non-functionalized reference, with an increase apparently proportional to the degree of functionalization. Considering that in **1-CNT** papers higher strength was observed although they contain no amides, the hydrogen bonding capabilities in **2-CNT** papers do not appear to appreciably contribute to the latter's tensile strength. Additionally, N-methylated **m2-**

Fig. 5. Strength of prepared CNT papers compared to type and degree of functionalization

CNT papers' strength was barely lower than that of their non-methylated counterpart, further precluding hydrogen bonding from playing a significant role in tensile strength. By contrast, **3-CNT** papers were the strongest despite their low degree of functionalization. Also, N-methylation here led to a drastic weakening of **m3-CNT** papers. Thus, hydrogen bonding after functionalization with **3** presumably plays an important role in the strength of corresponding CNT papers.

In SEM micrographs (Fig. 6), the effects of functionalization on the surface microstructure of the various CNT papers are discernible. The non-functionalized reference sample displays a fully random arrangement of nanotube bundles with no apparent order. A comparable random arrangement is observed in both the **2-CNT** and the N-methylated **m2-CNT** material. The **2-CNT** paper, however, shows an increase in bundle diameter and a coarsening of visible features. This effect is even more distinct in the **m2-CNT** paper, where the coarsening is enhanced. The most striking changes in microstructure, however, can be seen in the **1-** and the **3-**functionalized samples. Both structures exhibit domains of locally ordered nanotube bundles formed during the filtration process. In the **1-CNT** papers, the domains are not prevalent and embedded in large

Fig. 6. Surface morphology of the prepared CNT paper types observed with SEM

unordered areas. By contrast, the **3-CNT** paper exhibits an almost continuous aligned domain structure with only isolated areas of disordered bundles. The occurrence of such domains, combined with the increased tensile strength observed in both samples, is taken as an indication for enhanced intertubular interactions resulting from functionalization.

While in highly functionalized **1-CNT** papers an increase in π - π interactions is deemed to be responsible, low functionalized **3-CNT** papers are believed to be stabilized by hydrogen bonding between amide groups. This notion is strengthened by the fact that N-methylation led to both a decrease in tensile strength and a loss of ordered domains.

4 Conclusions

SWCNTs were functionalized by reaction with aromatic diazonium salts. Tensile tests on the corresponding CNT papers revealed that the Young's modulus was largely unaffected by functionalization. Tensile strength on the other hand did increase significantly, depending of the degree and/or type of functionalization. Highest tensile strength was observed for CNTs functionalized with sidegroups containing two amide linkages, in spite of the comparatively low degree of functionalization. By contrast, no gain was noted with sidegroups containing one amide linkage, thus considered not effective in forming hydrogen bonds to adjacent CNTs. The influence of hydrogen bonding on the strength was further evidenced by N-methylation, resulting in material of low strength. SEM analysis revealed the presence of ordered domains in the surface structure of the strongest CNT papers, further supporting the notion, that enhanced intertubular interaction are responsible for the high mechanical properties. N-methylation of amide functionalized CNTs led to significantly better dispersibility in NMP, a finding deemed important with regard to wet processing of CNTs.

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